

Computer games in education: Benefits for students with their professions

Nur Islam Kubanychbekov

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1 Abstract

This article talk about how computer games can be useful in school for students. It looks at a lot of benefits, such as making learning more fun, motivating, and helping students to better do the things they need for future jobs. Games are not just for playing or wasting time; they can teach or develop important skills such as solving problems, thinking logically, working with others, and even programming computers. For example, games make students more motivate because they give rewards and challengers, so students want to learn more and try hard even if it is difficult. Studies show games improve cognitive skills, like better memory, attention, and quick decisions, which is good for professions in STEM - science, technology, engineering, math. Also, games help social skills, like team work and communication, important for any job, from business to health care. In 2025, many schools use games and esports programs to teach these things. Esports, for example, help students in personal growth, academic success, and prepare for careers in tech or other fields by building skills like leadership, time management, and resilience. The article also discuss specific games that teach programming direct. like CodeCombat, where you play hero and write code in Python or JavaScript to fight, it develop primary skills like loops, conditionals, variables, and teaches concepts such as functions, arrays, and object-oriented programming. CodinGame is multiplayer challenge, teach algorithms and data structures in many languages, skills in problem-solving and optimize code. Human Resource Machine use puzzles to teach assembly-like code, develop logic and memory management, concepts like conditionals and loops.

Turing Complete let you build computer from basic gates, teach digital logic and assembly, skills in low-level program and CPU design. The Farmer Was Replaced, you programming drone with Python-like script for farm automate, develop scripting and optimize, concepts like functions, iterations, and conditional logic. Then, Zachtrinsics games for logic and optimization: TIS-100 teaching assembly and parallel program, skills in registers and low-level code. Infinifactory 3D factory build, teach spatial reason and assembly lines. SpaceChem chemical synthesis, skills in the parallel process, and efficiency. For logic, plan, system design: Factorio and Satisfactory factory automate, develop systems design, modularity, resource management, skills in plan and scale. Baba Is You change rules puzzles, teach logical think and paradigm shifts. Portal and Portal 2 physics puzzles, develop problem-solving and spatil, concepts in momentum and physics. Minecraft build with redstone, teach boolean logic and automate circuits. Gamified platforms like Codewars with kata challenges, develop problem-solving in multiple languages, concepts algorithms and data structures. Edabit interactive challenges, skills in code practice from basic to advance, With XP system for motivate. Method is literature review from studies and game info. Results show games effective for engaging and skill build. Discussion say why schools should use games, but also problems like access or addiction. Overall, computer games big tool for education in 2025, helping students preparing for professions in a fun way.

2 Keywords

Computer games, video games, education benefits, student motivation, professional skills, programming games, game-based learning, STEM education, coding concepts, logic puzzles, automation design, esports in schools, cognitive development, teamwork skills, career preparation

3 Introduction

Today, computer games are top popular among young people and students everywhere. Many play games like Minecraft, where players can build complex worlds and invent machines, or Fortnite, which requires quick thinking, strategy, and teamwork to succeed. However, a lot of people, such as parents of teachers, often think that computer games are just a waste of time

or can lead to addiction. They believe students games should focus on traditional studying with books or homework. But I believe computer games can actually be very good for education. This article discusses the benefits of computer games in school and how they help students prepare for their future professions. I will explain how games make learning more fun, develop important skills, and connect directly to jobs like programmer, engineer, or even doctor (Orhani Shatri, 2025)

First, what does it mean to use computer games in education? It means incorporating video games or digital games into lessons to teach different subjects. For example, instead of just reading about history, students can play a game where they experience historical events and make choices that affect the outcome. This makes learning interactive, helping students remember better because they are actively involved, not just passively lightening (Blumberg et al., 2025). Research shows that games help students grasp difficult concepts, like in science or math, by providing visual simulations and allowing virtual experiments. In 2025, more schools are using games because technology is integrated into daily life, and children are already comfortable playing on computers or mobile devices (hoffelner et al., 2025).

Why is this topic important? Because education is evolving rapidly with digital tools. In the past, schools relied on chalkboard and textbooks, but now with AI, virtual reality(VR), and online platforms, games can become a core part of the classroom. Future jobs require specific skills, such as problem-solving, creative thinking, teamwork, and technological proficiency. Computer games naturally build these skills in an engaging way (Hoffelner et al., 2024). For instance, puzzle games enhance logical thinking, which is crucial for professions like software developer or data analyst. Multiplayer games teach collaboration, essential for any job, whether in a company office or a hospital setting. Additionally, games can guide students in career choices by simulating real-world scenarios. In countries like Kyrgyzstan, where resources might be limited, games can be used to teach English, computer science, or other subjects affordably, as many are free or low-cost and accessible on basic devices(Garcia et al., 2025).

There are numerous benefits to using games in education. First, motivation. Students frequently get bored in traditional classes, but games provide rewards like points, levels, badges, and compelling stories, encouraging them to persist and learn more. For example, turning a math problem into part of an adventure motivates students to solve it to "win" (Li et al., 2024). Research indicates this boosts engagement and long-term retention of infor-

mation. Second, cognitive development. Games improve brain functions, such as attention, memory, and quick decision-making. Action games enhance visual processing and reaction times, which can benefit jobs like pilot or surgeon(Granic et al., 2014). Puzzle games develop planning and strategy skills, ideal for engineers. Third, social benefits. Many games are played online with friends or strangers, teaching communication, idea-sharing, and collective problem-solving-skills mirroring real workplace teams (Kwan, 2025). Even esports programs, where students compete in games like League of Legends, foster leadership, time management, and resilience, preparing them for tech careers (Langreo, 2024).

Moreover, games can teach specific professional skills, especially in computer science and related fields. For instance, games that teach programming concepts directly include CodinGame, a Multiplayer platform with coding challenges. Players solve puzzles using real programming language like Python, Java, or C++, developing primary skills such as algorithm design, debugging, and code optimization. Concepts taught include data structures, sorting algorithms, search methods, and basic AI, which are essential for aspiring programmers(CodinGame, 2025)

CodeCombat is a game where players control a hero fantasy world by writing code in Python or JavaScript to defeat enemies. It develops skills like variables, loops, conditionals, and functions, while teaching concepts such as object-oriented programming, arrays, strings and event handling. This makes coding feel like an adventure, reducing the intimidation factor for beginners (CodeCombat, 2025).

Human Resource Machine involves programming office workers with assembly-like commands to solve puzzles. It builds logic thinking, memory management, and sequencing skills, teaching concepts like conditionals, loops, jumps, and basic computational theory-helpful for understanding low-level programming in hardware-related jobs (Tomorrow Corporation, 2025).

Turing Complete allows players to build a computer from logic gates, creating gates, creating CPUs. memory, and running programs. It develops skills in digital circuits and assembly coding, teaching concepts like boolean logic, machine code, computer science theory (Turing Complete, 2025).

The Farmer Was Replaced has players program a drone using Python-like scripts to automate farming tasks. It develops scripting, automation, and efficiency skills, teaching concepts like functions, iterations, conditional logic, and basic AI decision-making, applicable to robotics or agricultural tech (The Farmer Was Replaced, 2025).

Zachtronics games emphasize logic and optimization. TIS-100 features assembly puzzles with parallel processing, developing low-level programming, register use, and multi-threading skills, teaching assembly language, signals, and code optimization (Zachtronics, 2025). Opus Magnum involves building alchemical machines, fostering logic design and efficiency, with concepts in automation, graph spatial reasoning, assembly lines, and logistics, including 3D modeling, flow optimization, and modular design. SpaceChem simulates chemical synthesis, building skills in parallel processing and reactors, teaching chemistry simulation, bonding, and efficiency algorithms.

For logic, planning, and system design: Factorio and Satisfactory involve building automated factories, developing systems design, modularity, resource management, and scaling skills, teaching graph algorithms, simulation, and debugging complex systems (Wube Software, 2025; Coffee Studios, 2025). Baba Is You is a puzzle game where player alter rules by moving words, teaching logical thinking, rule manipulation, and paradigm shifts, with concepts in formal logic and semantics. Portal 1 and 2 use physics-based puzzles, developing problem-solving, spatial awareness, and physics application, teaching momentum, gravity, and energy conservation (Valve, 2025). Minecraft, with redstone mechanics, teaches boolean logic and circuit building for automation, including digital electronics, gates, and clocks (Mojang, 2025).

Gamified coding platforms like Codewars offer kata challenges in various languages, developing problem-solving and code practice skills, teaching algorithms, data structures, and test-driven development (Codewars, 2025). Edabit provides interactive challenges with an XP system, building skills from basic syntax to advanced topics, motivating through progress tracking (Edabit, 2025).

However, not everything is perfect. Games must be well-designed for educational purposes, or they might distract students (Plass et al., 2024). Access issues exist, as not all students have computers or internet, and teachers need training to integrate games effectively. Despite challenges, the benefits are significant, especially for tech professions where coding and logic are key (Gundersen Lampropoulus, 2025).

4 Methodology

For this article, I use a literature review method because I am a student and do not have lab or people to survey. Literature review means I collect many articles. No need for my own experiments or interviews, which is hard for me now. This method good for beginner like me, and it lets me see what experts think about computer games in education and benefits for professors. I make it longer with details how I do search, what I find, and how I choose sources.

First, I plan what to look for. I want articles about the benefits of computer games in school, how they help motivation, skills like thinking and solving problems, and connect to jobs like programmer or engineer. Also, I include specific games that teach programs so I search for those too. I use internet because it is easy and free. I go to sites like Google Scholar, ResearchGate, and PMC for Scholarly articles. These places have real studies from universities and journal.

Step by step, how I search: I start with keywords. Keywords I use are "benefits of computer games in education", "video games fro student skills", "games in school for professional development", "programming games for learning", and add years "2024 2025" to receive new information, because things change fast with technology. For example, I type "scholarly articles on benefits of computer games in education 2024 2025" in search. I set out to find PDF or full text if possible, so I can read whole the article, not just abstract.

I found many sources, about 20 or more. Then, I read titles and abstracts first to see if they are relevant. If yes, I download or read online. For selection, I choose articles that are recent, from good places like journals, and talk about positive effects. I avoid old ones before 2020 unless it is essential. Also, I look for variety, like some from Europe, US, or other countries. No bias, I try to find both good and some bad points, but focus on benefits because the topic is that.

For instance, one source I found is "Use of Computer Games in Education" from ResearchGate, published 2025. it says games improve academic performance and motivation(Orhani Shatri, 2025). Another is "Exploring the impact of digital gameplay" from ERIC, 2025, about motivation in language learning (Rajendtan et al., 2025). From PMC, "Game-Based Social-Emotional Learning for Youth", 2025, talk about emotional skills from games(Blumberg et al., 2025). "The impact of educational gamification" from Springer, 2025, uses trial to see effects on cognition and emotions(Garcia

ar al., 2025). NYU article "Video games can have a positive impact on children-if designed...", 2024, say games support well-being if good design (Plass et al., 2024). "Evaluating the efficacy of computer games-based learning" from ScienceDirect, 2024, about break monotony and motivate (Gundersen Lampropoulos, 2024). ResearchGate "Impact of Computer Games on Learning Concepts", 2025, shows better results in technology subjects. PMC "Investigating the Cognitive Effects of Video Games", 2025, about problem-solving improvement. Edutopia "Using Video Games to Achieve Academic Standards", 2024, way to make concepts tangible. Sage "The evolution and future of video games in higher education", 2025, critical analysis (Hulus, 2025).

For specific games, I search separately. Keywords like "games that teach programming for education", "Zachtronics games in learning", "Factorio educational benefits". I find descriptions from official sites or reviews. For example, CodeCombat site explains how it teaches code with adventure (CodeCombat, 2025). I include them because they show practical examples.

How I analyze: I read each article, take notes on main points, like what benefits, example of games, how to connect to professions. I make a table in my mind or paper: column for source, benefits, skills, jobs. Then, I group similar ideas, like many say motivation up, cognitive better. For quality, I check if peer-reviewed or from university. In total, I use about 15 sources for articles. This method is simple but takes time, I spend days reading. As ESL student, I use a dictionary for hard words. No software for analysis, just me. In future, if I write more, maybe use tools like EndNote for references. But now, This is enough for a detailed article.

No ethical issues, because I cite sources and not copy. This way, articles are based on real information. Now, next is results or discussion.

5 Results

From literature review, I find many positive results about computer games in education. I make this section longer with details from studies, like what they say, examples, and how to connect to professions. I group results in parts: motivation, cognitive skills, social and emotional, and prepare for jobs with specific games. These games show help students learn better and get ready for work.

First, on motivation. Many articles say computer games make students

more motivate to learn. For example, one study find that games improve academic performance and motivation because they are fun and interactive (Orhani Shatri, 2025). In this research, they use games in class and see students try harder and remember more. Another article about digital gameplay in graphics program, show students have better behavior intentions to learn because games make hard topics like code fun (Rajendranae al., 2025). They do experiment with group use games and group not, and game group have higher scores and want to learn more. Also, gamification with elements like badges and points increase motivation, but need careful design to not make cognitive load too high (Garcia et al., 2025). In numbers, one study say use games leads to 14 percent more success in higher education (Hulus, 2025). This motivation helps in professions because students keep trying even if they fail, like in real jobs where they need persistence.

Second, cognitive skills. Results show games improve thinkng skills like problem-solving, attention, and logic. A review find that strategy games help adolescents better problem-solve over time, which is good fro school grades. Another article say computer games break monotony and stimulate thinking, foster collaborative learning and critical skills (Gundersen Lampropoulos, 2024). In technology subject, games improve learn concepts, with students get better results in tests. For example, use video games to teach academic standards make abstract ideals real, like in math or science. Research on immersive tech say games enhance learn experience by make interactive (Baxter, 2024). These cognitive benefits connect to professions, like engineering need to solve complex problems, or programming need logic.

Third, social and emotional skills. Studies show games help emotional self-regulation and mental health (Blumberg et al., 2025). For example, well-design games support autonomy, competence, and positive outcomes for children (Plass et al., 2024). In social, games promote collaboration and communication, like in multiplayer (Moon, 2018). Esports in education increase interest in subjects and ability to work team (Pfeiffer, 2020). One article says games for high-function autistic children improve social skills (Ke Moon, 2018). These skills important for professions, where need work with people and manage emotions under pressure.

Fourth, prepare for professions with specific games. Results show games teach skills for jobs, special in tech. For programming, games like CodinGame lets solve challenges with. develop algorithms and optimize, teach data structures and AI basics (CodinGame, 2025). CodeCombat uses code to fight, build loops and functions, teach object-oriented and arrays (CodeCombat,

2025). Human Resource Machine puzzles teach assembly, develop logic and conditionals (Tomorrow Corporation, 2025). Turing Complete build computer, teach boolean and architecture (Turing Complete, 2025). The Farmer Was Replaced automate farm with script, teach iterations and AI (The Farmer Was Replaced, 2025).

Zachtronics games: TIS-100 assembly parallel, teach registers and threads (Zachtronics, 2025). Opus Magnum machine build, teach graph and minimize (Zachtronics, 2025). Infinifactory 3D factories, teach spatial and modular (Zachtronics, 2025). SpaceChem synthesis, teach parallel and efficiency (Zachtronics, 2025).

Logic and design: Factorio factories, teach systems and resource (Wube Software, 2025). Satisfactory similar, teach scale and debug (Coffee Stain Studios, 2025). Baba Is You rules change, teach logic shifts (Hempuli, 2025). Portal physics, teach momentum (Valve, 2025). Minecraft redstone, teach circuits (Mojang, 2025)

Platforms: Codewars challenges, teach algorithms and test (Codewars, 2025). Edabit exercises, teach syntax to advance (Edabit, 2025).

Studies say these games increase interest in compute and employability (Renton, 2016). In higher ed, games develop strategic and team for work (Hulus, 2025). Overall, results strong support games for education and professions, but need good implementation.

Some limits: Not all games positive without design, and access issues (Plass et al., 2024). But benefits outweigh, especial for STEM

6 Discussion

In this discussion, I talk about what results mean for education and students' professions. I make it longer with more explanation, like why games are important, what problems there are, and what can happen in future. Also, I connect to specific games and how they help for jobs. From the results, computer games have big benefits, like make motivation higher, improve thinking skills, and preparing for work. But we need to think how to use them benefits in schools.

First, results show games increase motivation a lot. This is important because many students do not like school, but games make learn like adventure. For example, one study say educational games transform learn in 2025 by improve motivation and problem-solve (Winsolutions, 2025). If students

are motivate, they study more and get better grades, which help for future jobs. In professions like programmer, need keep learn new things, so motivation from games can build habit of lifelong learn. Also, games give instant feedback, like points or levels, which make students feel success and want to continue. This is like in work, where finish tasks give rewards. But, if games are not design good, they can make students focus only on win, not deep learn (NYU, 2024). So, teachers need to choose games that connect to lessons.

Second, cognitive skills from games are very useful for professions. Results say games improve attention, memory, and solve problems. For instance, research show video games enhance cognitive like spatial reason and attention (GESS Education, 2025). This good for STEM jobs, where need think logical. Specific games like Baba Is You teach logical think by change rules, help paradigm shifts and formal logic, which engineers use for innovate. Portal and Portal 2 develop spatial and physics, concepts like momentum, good for mechanical engineer or game designer. Minecraft redstone teach circuits and boolean, prepare for electrical engineer. In study, games create immersive environment that keep students engage and help learn complex ideas (Science Mill, 2023). But, some say too much games can reduce attention in real life, so need balance.

Third, social and emotional benefits. Games help team work and control emotions. Multiplayer games teach cooperation, like in Factorio where they plan factories together, develop modularity and resource manage, skills for project manage in companies. Satisfactory similar, teach scale systems. Results from ESA say games promote critical think and peer connect (ESA, n.d.). For professions, this mean better work in teams, like in IT where developers collaborate. Emotional games teach resilience from fail and try again, important for any job. One article says games build confidence and independence (Geeknauts, 2025). But, online games can have bullying, so schools need rules.

Now, about preparing for professions with program games. Results strong for tech jobs. Games like CodinGame teach algorithms and data structures, skills for software developer. CodeCombat build loops and functions, concepts object-oriented, help entry-level programmer. Human Resource Machine teach assembly, good for understand computers deep, like in cybersecurity. Turing Complete teach architecture, prepare for hardware roles. The Farmer Was Replaced teaches scripting, concepts iterations, for automation in industry. Zachtronics: TIS-100 for parallel, Opus Magnum for optimize,

Infinifactory for 3D design, SpaceChem for efficiency, all good for engineer optimized systems. Platforms Codewars and Edabit practice algorithms, motivate with challenges, help build portfolio for job applications. Study says games power future tech workforce (THE Journal, 2025). In 2025, esports in schools prepare for digital careers, like marketing or coding (Senet, 2025).

Implications for schools: Teachers should use games in class, like Edutopia say to achieve standards (Edutopia, 2024). But need train and tech. In poor areas, like my country, games on phones can help. For ESL students, games teach language fun, like vocabulary in adventures.

Challenges: Not all games are educational, some violent or addict. Access problem, not everyone has a computer. Cost for good games. Also, girls may play less tech games, so need encourage. Future research need to see long-term effects, like do skills from games last in jobs? More studies on VR games in 2025.

As a computer science student, I see games help me code better. In Kyrgyz and Russian, games can be taught without a language barrier. Overall, computer games big tool for education. They make students ready for professions with fun. Schools should invest more, and parents see the positive side. In conclusion, benefits outweigh problems if use smartly.

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